

Spectrophotometric and Conductometric Studies of Metal Complexes of 3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazeno. Part VI. Cobalt Complex

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Cobalt forms a brown, water-soluble complex with 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazeno with an absorbance peak at 390 m μ and a flat region from 450 to 485 m μ . The *pH* range of constant maximum absorbance is between 4.3 and 5.0. The system obeys Beer's law in the concentration range of 0.8 to 10 p.p.m. of cobalt at 480 m μ and the molecular extinction coefficient is 4.833×10^5 . Most of the commonly associated ions do not interfere at this wave length. Sandell's spectrophotometric sensitivity is 0.195 γ /cm². The formula of the complex, established spectrophotometrically, is CoR₃ (R=reagent) and conductometrically, CoR₁ and CoR₂ are also indicated. The dissociation constant of CoR₃ at 25° is 2.546×10^{-13} and the free energy of complex formation is -17.17 kcal/mole at 25°.

3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazeno forms a brown, water-soluble complex with cobalt. The complex formation is almost instantaneous and it is stable towards time and temperature. Full colour development is ensured at 1:6 ratio of cobalt to reagent. It has an absorbance peak at 390 m μ and a flat region from 450 to 485 m μ . The reagent interferes up to 425 m μ . The complexes of copper, nickel, palladium, manganese, titanium, and molybdate have absorbance up to 475 m μ and thus interfere. Hence 480 m μ is considered to be a suitable wave length for cobalt estimation. The complex formation has been, however, studied at 430 m μ without any difficulty.

In previous parts of the series¹, the complex formation with palladium, molybdenum, copper, iron, and nickel were reported. In the present investigation the use of the reagent for spectrophotometric determination of cobalt has been described. The formula of the complex has been established spectrophotometrically as CoR₃. The chelate structure may be represented as:

Conductometrically, besides CoR₃, CoR₁, and CoR₂ are also indicated.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard cobalt solution was prepared by dissolving approximately 4.6 g. of reagent grade cobalt nitrate hexahydrate in 250 ml of water and the metal content was determined gravimetrically, using 1-nitroso-2-naphthol. It was diluted to give $M \times 10^{-3}$

1. *This Journal*, 1958, 35, 542, 859; 1959, 36, 269; 1960, 37, 117; 1963, 40, 213.

solution. The reagent solution, buffer solutions, instruments, etc. were the same as described in Part I'.

Spectral Characteristics of Cobalt Complex.—Equal volumes of cobalt solution ($M \times 10^{-3}$) and the reagent solution ($M \times 10^{-2}$) (3 ml, each) were taken in a 50-ml flask. Suitable quantities of 10% HCl and 10% sodium acetate were added so that pH after dilution was about 5. Absorbance was measured, using reagent solution of the same strength and pH as blank. Fig. 1, curve b shows the absorbance of cobalt complex with 'reagent-blank solution' and curve a, that of the reagent solution with water as blank. Absorbance of the reagent solution falls sharply after 390 m μ and is negligible at 425 m μ . The absorbance peak of cobalt complex is at 390 m μ ; it then falls and has a flat region from 450 to 485 m μ . Even in this region, the absorbance is fairly high to be suitable for cobalt estimations.

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

Reagent Ratio for Maximum Absorbance.—A series of solutions was prepared as described earlier in which mole ratio of cobalt to reagent varied from 1:1 to 1:10. Fig. 2, curve a shows the effect of increase of concentration of the reagent on absorbance. Maximum absorbance was obtained at 1:6 ratio of metal to reagent.

Effect of pH.—Solutions containing the same concentrations of cobalt and the reagent were prepared as described above at different pH values and their absorbance was measured at 430 m μ . The range of constant maximum absorbance was from pH 4.3 to 5.9.

Rate of Reaction and Stability of the Complex.—The full colour development of cobalt complex was almost instantaneous and there was no difference in absorbance taken after 24 hours.

Effect of Temperature.—There was no difference in absorbance of the sample prepared at room temperature and that heated on a water bath to 85°. The complex was stable over a wide range of temperature variations.

Beer's Law.—Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range of 0.8 to 10 p.p.m. of cobalt at 480 m μ . The molecular extinction coefficient of cobalt complex at this wave length was 4.833×10^3 .

Sensitivity.—Sandell's spectrophotometric sensitivity² was obtained by dividing

² Sandell, "Colorimetric Determination of Traces of Metals", 3rd ed., Interscience Publ., New York, 1959.

molecular weight of the complex by its molecular extinction coefficient and was found to be 0.195 γ /cm².

Recommended Procedure.—Cobalt solution containing 20 to 250 γ of the metal was taken in a 25-ml flask. 10% HCl and 10% sodium acetate were added in suitable amounts so that the pH of the final solution was between 4.3 and 5.9; 10 ml of 0.1% reagent solution in water was then added. The volume was made to the mark and the absorbance was read at 480 m μ , using water as blank.

Tolerance of Diverse Ions.—The reagent reacted with most of the common metal ions in slightly acidic medium to provide complexes which had absorbance from 390 to 475 m μ . Hence to increase the selectivity of the reagent, 480 m μ was considered a suitable wave length for estimating cobalt in presence of diverse ions. Table I records the results. The interference due to Fe³⁺ was removed by masking it with 1 ml of 5% sodium fluoride solution.

TABLE I
Tolerance of diverse ions.

Ion added as.		Conc. of ion (p.p.m.).	Ion added as.		Conc. of ion (p.p.m.).
Cu ²⁺	Sulphate	100	Al ³⁺	Sulphate	200
Ni ²⁺	Chloride	50	Cr ³⁺	"	100
Zn ²⁺	Acetate	200	Pd ²⁺	Chloride	30
Mn ²⁺	Chloride	150	Sodium	Molybdate	50
Fe ³⁺	Sulphate	30	Tungstate	"	200

Composition of the Complex

Nature of the Complex Formed.—In a set of experiments, mixtures containing varying proportions of cobalt: reagent were prepared at different pH values and the optical densities at different wave lengths in each case were measured. In all the cases, nature of the absorbance curves was the same, thus indicating formation of only one complex with the reagent responsible for the colour³.

*Job's Method*⁴.—A series of solutions was prepared from $M \times 10^{-3}$ of the metal and the reagent in which the ratios of cobalt to reagent varied from 1:11 to 11:1. The pH was kept at about 5. Absorbance was measured at 430 and 450 m μ . Fig. 3 shows the curves obtained. The maxima at 3:9 ratio of cobalt to reagent indicate the formation of CoR₃.

*Molar Ratio Method*⁵.—Curve b, in Fig. 2 was obtained by adding 1 ml of 1M-KCl solution in the experiment described earlier. A break was obtained at a ratio of three moles of the reagent to one mole of cobalt.

Conductance Method.—The method was the same as described in Part IV¹. The formation of three complexes: CoR₁, CoR₂, and CoR₃ was indicated during the course of the reaction.

3. Vosburgh and Cooper, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, **63**, 437.

4. *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **x**, 9, 113.

5. Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.

FIG. 3
pH = 5.0. R = reagent.

DISCUSSION

The dissociation of the complex may be written as:

where C is the concentration of the complex, assuming no dissociation, and α is the degree of dissociation. From Fig. 2, curve a

$$\alpha = \frac{E_m - E_s}{E_m} = \frac{0.29 - 0.22}{0.29} = 0.241.$$

The dissociation constant is given by the relation:

$$K = \frac{C\alpha \times (3\alpha C)^3}{C(1-\alpha)} = \frac{27\alpha^4 C^3}{1-\alpha} = \frac{27(0.241)^4 (6 \times 10^{-3})^3}{0.259}$$

Hence the dissociation constant is equal to 2.546×10^{-3} at 25° .

The standard free energy of formation of the complex from cobalt nitrate and the reagent is calculated from the relation $\Delta F = RT \ln K$, where K is the dissociation constant and works out to -17.17 kcal./mole at 25° .

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